

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

Programme	EU4HEALTH
Project number	101080009
Acronym	CAN.HEAL
Start Date	1 Nov 2022
Duration	24 months (+ 6 month extension)

Deliverable information

WP	5
Deliverable related number	5.4
Deliverable number	5.4
Deliverable name	Regulations and recommendations related to remote and face-to-face genetic counselling quality, access, and sustainability
Deliverable Description	Recommendations for improving the quality, access and sustainability of face-to-face and remote genetic counselling across EU Member States. Paper, English
Lead Beneficiary	MHH-GER
Type	R – Document, report
Dissemination level	Public
Version	1
Due Date	31 December 2024
Delivery Date	03 December 2024
Approval Date	

Revision History			
Version	Date	Comments	Partner
1	03 December 2024		MHH-Ger

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Executive Summary

Genetic counselling is critical to the effective integration of genetic and genomic technologies into cancer care, providing a human interface point that enables patients to make informed decisions about how to engage with these technologies. Missing and poor-quality counselling leads to avoidable costs (*e.g. unnecessary genetic tests*), inaccurate diagnoses, suboptimal clinical management, and negative psychosocial outcomes in both patients and family members. Common European barriers to high-quality genetic counselling in cancer were identified in preliminary work (Deliverable 5.3 + survey of cancer patient organizations): genetic literacy (*of patients and non-genetics health professionals*); workforce capacity; and insurance reimbursement. Through a Delphi survey of 77 genetics, oncology, and patient stakeholders from all 27 Member States, five priority European solutions were identified to address these barriers:

- 1) EU-wide recognition of genetic counsellors
- 2) Mandatory inclusion of genetics expertise in the creation and updating of oncology guidelines
- 3) EU system of registration, accreditation, and education for genetic counsellors
- 4) Mandatory fellowship and continuing education in genetics for oncologists
- 5) Mandatory full reimbursement of genetic counselling when clinical guidelines are met

Feasibility ratings from Delphi survey participants indicate that changes to oncology guidelines and fellowship/continuing education will likely be the most straightforward and quickest to implement. Solutions related to reimbursement and genetic counsellor recognition/registration/accreditation/education are still high priority but will likely

require more extended timeframes and additional effort to ensure sustainable implementation. Immediate next steps are proposed for each solution, including mapping, multi-stakeholder discussion, and economic analysis activities.

Objective of the deliverable

Provide recommendations for how to best address common European barriers to genetic counselling quality, access, and sustainability in cancer, as identified in our prior work: genetic literacy; workforce capacity; and reimbursement.

Work performed

Context & Prior Work

Genetic counselling is critical to the effective integration of genetic and genomic technologies into cancer care, providing a human interface point that enables patients to make informed decisions about how to engage with these technologies.¹ Low-quality genetic counseling, including counselling by individuals with insufficient genetics expertise, has been demonstrated to negatively impact care. Specifically, low-quality counselling leads to avoidable costs (*e.g. unnecessary genetic tests*), inaccurate diagnoses, suboptimal clinical management, and negative psychosocial outcomes in patients and family members.²

An increasing demand for genetic testing linked to the push to personalized medicine³ is necessarily associated with an increasing demand for genetic counselling. However, shortages of clinical/medical genetics expertise across EU Member States noted as

recently as 2020 underscore the need for new strategies to ensure that high quality genetic counselling can be provided in sufficient volumes across the EU.^{4,5} Absent these new approaches, genetic counselling risks becoming a bottleneck constraining the implementation of genetic technologies and personalized approaches in cancer prevention and treatment.

Deliverable 5.3 – legislation and health professional perspective

As a foundation for the development of new genetic counselling strategies, Deliverable 5.3 provided an overview of genetic counselling legislation and practice in cancer in all 27 European Union Member States. This overview was compiled based on searches of national legislative databases and an interview survey of genetics health professionals in each Member State. A version of this deliverable was also published in the European Journal of Public Health.⁶

This overview described diverse approaches to legislation/regulation of genetic counselling across Member States, which was also reflected by substantial variation in genetic counselling practice across Member States (*e.g. who delivers counselling, when counselling is provided, how counselling is provided*). The approach to remote genetic counselling (i.e. ‘telegenetics’) was more consistent across Member States. Telegenetic counselling is legally permitted in 25 of 27 Member States but utilized predominantly in circumstances of patient preference; genetic counselling is delivered mostly face-to-face in a majority of Member States (17 of 27; 63%).

Notwithstanding these varied approaches to counselling legislation/regulation and delivery, three common European barriers to genetic counselling in cancer were identified: genetic literacy (of patients and non-genetics health professionals)(*noted in*

all 27 Member States); workforce capacity (*noted in 25 of 27 Member States*); and, to a more varied extent, insurance reimbursement (*noted in 13 of 27 Member States*).

Patient Perspective

To complement the perspectives of genetics health professionals from Deliverable 5.3, the perspectives of patients were sought through an online survey of cancer patient organizations in the European Union. Specifically, this survey aimed to identify the perceived patient barriers to accessing genetic counselling in a cancer context to evaluate the alignment of patient and health professional perspectives.

At least one cancer patient organization in each Member State which represents patients likely to have interacted with genetic services during their cancer treatment was invited to participate by email between April and August 2024. In most Member States, a 'national cancer patient organization' identified by their membership in the Association of European Cancer Leagues was contacted. In some Member States, organizations representing patients with specific cancer types (e.g. breast, myeloma) or genetic mutations (e.g. BRCA) were also contacted. The central objective was, similar to Deliverable 5.3, to solicit the perspectives of at least one relevant organization in as many Member States as possible.

The full survey is included in Appendix A for reference. In summary, fixed response questions (multiple choice; 0-10 rating) covered the following domains: when counselling is provided (pre-test, post-test); who provides counselling; insurance barriers; preferred genetic counselling delivery mode; waiting times for counselling; psychosocial support; and genetic literacy resources. Additionally, free text fields provided opportunities for further comments regarding additional barriers to genetic

counselling and important changes which could be made to address barriers to quality and access.

In total, representatives of cancer patient organizations from 20 Member States completed the survey (1 organization per Member State), from a total of 34 invited organizations. We did not receive a response from organizations in Austria, Czech Republic, Estonia, France, Ireland, Lithuania, and Slovakia. Survey responses from cancer patient organizations were well aligned with the perspectives of health professionals detailed in Deliverable 5.3 – variation in genetic counselling practice (*i.e. who, when, how*), but consistent genetic literacy, workforce capacity, and insurance reimbursement barriers to access across Member States.

Specifically, organizations in 17 of 20 surveyed Member States (85%) noted that additional resources genetic literacy resources for patients/families are ‘very much needed’ (≥ 7 out of 10 on scale from ‘0 – not needed’ to ‘10 – very much needed’). Additionally, organizations in 17 of 20 Member States (85%) considered waiting times for genetic counselling to be ‘too long’ in one or more clinical scenarios, suggesting insufficient workforce capacity to meet genetic counselling demands. Further, organizations in 12 of 20 Member States (60%) noted that cost or insurance coverage was a barrier to patients receiving genetic counselling for predictive testing. Organizations in 6 of 20 Member States (30%) noted cost/insurance barriers for genetic counselling in a treatment scenario.

Cancer patient organizations in 14 of 20 surveyed Member States (70%) indicated that most patients in their country prefer face-to-face pre-test genetic counselling; a similar proportion of Member States provide mostly face-to-face counselling (63%; Deliverable 5.3⁶). Organizations in almost all Member States (19 of 20; 95%) reported that most patients would prefer to receive face-to-face post-test counselling in case of

significant findings. Organizations in 11 of 20 Member States (55%) noted that a majority of patients in their country still would prefer face-to-face post-test counselling if no significant findings are uncovered.

Common European Barriers to Genetic Counselling in Cancer

Deliverable 5.3 and the survey of cancer patient organizations described above demonstrate alignment between genetics health professionals and cancer patient organizations across the EU regarding three common European barriers to genetic counselling quality and access in cancer: genetic literacy (of patients and/or non-genetics health professionals); workforce capacity; and, to a more varied extent, insurance reimbursement. See **Figure 1** for a summary.

Figure 1. Common European barriers to genetic counselling in cancer, as noted by genetics health professionals (left panel) and representatives of cancer patient organizations in European Union Member States.

Delphi Survey of Key Stakeholders – A Consensus-Building Foundation for Recommendations

The three common European barriers identified in above provide clear targets for European action aiming to ensure the sustainable delivery of high-quality and accessible genetic counselling. The prevalence of these barriers across Member States indicates that European-level action may be the most efficient approach to addressing these barriers. With this in mind, we conducted a Delphi survey of key genetics, oncology, and patient stakeholders from across the European Union to generate European solutions to these three common European barriers.

Participants

At least one individual from each Member State was invited to participate in this Delphi survey from each of the following three groups: clinical/medical geneticist physicians; clinical/medical oncologist physicians; cancer patient organization. Clinical/medical genetics and oncology physicians in leadership positions of national genetics and oncology societies were invited from each Member State, as well as additional physicians known to the CAN.HEAL consortium as possessing expertise in genetic counselling in cancer (e.g. through prior work⁶). Further, at least one genetic counsellor (allied health professional) was invited from the 15 Member States in which genetic counsellors are active.⁷

Methods

A modified 'Policy Delphi' process was used to solicit participant input and feedback regarding solutions to common European literacy, workforce, and reimbursement barriers to genetic counselling. Given the large number of invited stakeholders, a structured approach was favored in both Phases, forgoing an initial phase of open-ended questions.⁸ In the first Phase of the Delphi survey, participants were asked to rate (1-9 Likert scale⁸) nine European solutions proposed by the research team according to their '*Importance (i.e. impact potential)*', '*Urgency (i.e. need for swift implementation)*', and '*Feasibility (i.e. ease of implementation)*':

- P1. EU-wide recognition of genetic counsellors as allied health professionals and appropriately qualified experts to deliver genetic counselling.
- P2. Establish an EU system of registration, education and accreditation for genetic counsellors (allied health professional) with legal weight in Member States
- P3. Establishment of target numbers of clinical/medical geneticist physicians per 100,000 population for Member States.
- P4. Mandate full reimbursement of genetic counselling when conducted according to national or European guidelines.
- P5. Mandate full reimbursement of genetic counselling regardless of delivery mode (e.g. remote, face-to-face) for both patients and clinicians/allied health professionals in each Member State.
- P6. Mandate the availability of genetics continuing professional education for non-genetics health professionals in each Member State.

- P7. Mandatory education for clinical oncologists – continuing and as a part of fellowship training – regarding screening for cancer predisposition syndromes (e.g. when to refer, how to screen).
- P8. Development and EU-wide implementation of a best-practice approach to genetics education in secondary students.
- P9. Mandatory inclusion of genetics expertise in the creation and revision of national/EU clinical oncology guidelines.

Participants had the option to provide additional text comments for each solution, as well as propose and rate (*Importance, Urgency, and Feasibility criteria; 1-9 Likert scale*) up to three additional solutions.

In the second phase of the Delphi survey, participants were presented with a summary of all Phase 1 ratings, and asked to rate (*Importance, Urgency, and Feasibility criteria; 1-9 Likert scale*) 10 further solutions aggregated around common themes from 64 participant proposals in Phase 1. Additionally, participants were asked to designate their #1, #2, and #3 priority solutions from the 19 solutions presented in Phase 1 and Phase 2 (*9 researcher-proposed solutions in Phase 1 + 10 participant-proposed solutions in Phase 2*).

Individual participant responses and identities were confidential, as is common practice in Delphi studies.⁸ A solution was defined a priori to reach ‘consensus’ high Importance and Urgency with an average rating >7 out of 9, in line with prior Delphi studies.⁸ No consensus criteria were defined for Feasibility ratings, but the following descriptors were ascribed to contextualize average Feasibility ratings: low feasibility (1-3); moderate feasibility (4-6); high feasibility (7-9).

The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis 1-way ANOVA was used to test for significant differences in Importance, Urgency, and Feasibility ratings between the four professional groups: clinical/medical geneticists; clinical/medical oncologists; genetic counsellors; cancer patient organization representatives. When significant main effects were found, pairwise comparisons between professional groups were performed using the non-parametric Dunn's test and Bonferroni correction for multiple comparisons. Significant differences between professional groups in priority rankings for each solution were interrogated using the chi-square test. Significance was set at $\alpha=0.05$ for all statistical tests, except where the Bonferroni correction was used. All statistical analyses were performed in SPSS version 29.0 (IBM Corporation).

Results

A total of 77 individuals accepted invitations to participate in Phase 1 of the Delphi survey, from 123 total invitations (62% response rate). The majority of participants were female (n=50; 65%) and aged 41-60 (n=57; 74%). In Phase 2, 66 individuals participated (86% retention rate). General professional participant demographics are shown below in **Table 1**.

MEMBER STATE	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS									
	Clinical/medical Geneticist		Clinical/medical Oncologist		Genetic Counsellor		Cancer Patient Organization		TOTAL	
	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 1	Phase 2	Phase 1	Phase 2
<i>Austria</i>	2	2	-	-	1	1	-	-	3	3
<i>Belgium</i>	2	2	1	1	3	3	-	-	6	6
<i>Bulgaria</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1
<i>Croatia</i>	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1
<i>Cyprus</i>	-	-	1	1	1	1	1	-	3	2
<i>Czech Republic</i>	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	2	2
<i>Denmark</i>	2	1	-	-	1	1	1	-	4	2
<i>Estonia</i>	-	-	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	1
<i>Finland</i>	2	2	-	-	-	-	1	1	3	3
<i>France</i>	1	1	2	2	1	1	-	-	4	4
<i>Germany</i>	2	1	1	1	1	1	-	-	4	3
<i>Greece</i>	-	-	1	1	-	-	1	1	2	2
<i>Hungary</i>	2	1	-	-	-	-	1	-	3	1
<i>Ireland</i>	-	-	1	1	3	2	1	1	5	4
<i>Italy</i>	2	2	1	-	-	-	1	1	5	4
<i>Latvia</i>	2	2	-	-	-	-	1	1	3	3
<i>Lithuania</i>	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	1
<i>Luxembourg</i>	1	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	3	2
<i>Malta</i>	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	3*	3*
<i>The Netherlands</i>	1	1	-	-	-	-	2	2	3	3
<i>Poland</i>	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	2	2
<i>Portugal</i>	-	-	-	-	1	1	1	1	2	2
<i>Romania</i>	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	1	5	5
<i>Slovakia</i>	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	-	2	1
<i>Slovenia</i>	1	1	1	1	-	-	-	-	2	2
<i>Spain</i>	-	-	1	1	1	1	-	-	2	2
<i>Sweden</i>	1	1	-	-	1	1	-	-	2	2
TOTAL	28	24	14	11	18	17	16	13	77	66

Table 1. Delphi survey participants, organized by Member State and professional group. Individuals with both clinical genetics and clinical oncology qualifications were counted only as clinical geneticists (*their primary practicing specialty*). Individuals in a leadership position of a national genetics or oncology society but without clinical qualifications were counted in the respective genetics or oncology professional group. Of the 28 clinical/medical geneticists participating in Phase 1, 13 were in leadership positions of their national clinical/medical genetics society. Of the 14 clinical/medical oncologists participating in Phase 1, 6 were in leadership positions of their national clinical/medical oncology society. * - final numbers for Malta include the participation of a Public Health Medicine Physician with experience in genetic counselling delivery.

Phase 1 ratings

Six solutions met consensus criteria (average rating >7) for both Importance and Urgency, with another two solutions meeting consensus criteria for Importance only (**Figure 2**). Genetic counsellors rated solutions P1 and P2 related to EU-wide recognition and education/accreditation of genetic counsellors as being significantly more Important and Urgent than clinical/medical geneticists ($p<.02$). Genetic counsellors also rated solution P1 (EU-wide genetic counsellor recognition) as being significantly more Urgent than clinical/medical oncologists ($p=.02$).

Additionally, cancer patient organization representatives rated genetics education programs for secondary students (P8) as being significantly more Important and Urgent than genetic counsellors ($p<.03$). A significant main effect of professional group was found for solution P7 ($p<.05$) – mandatory education for clinical oncologists – but without any significant pairwise intergroup differences after correcting for multiple comparisons.

Phase 2 ratings

The following 10 additional solutions were aggregated from 64 total proposals from Delphi participants in Phase 1 and presented to participants for rating in Phase 2. Solutions aggregated from greater numbers of individual inputs are listed first (*e.g. the greatest number of individuals (7) independently proposed solutions related to online educational genetic counselling materials, so aggregated solutions on this topic are listed first*):

- A1. EU support for the creation and hosting of online genetic counselling educational materials to **support** counselling delivered face-to-face or by phone/video.
- A2. EU support for the creation and hosting of online genetic counselling materials aiming to **provide** counselling in common pre- and/or post-test scenarios.
- A3. EU-wide assessment of barriers and approaches to increasing the attractiveness of health professions and the retention of health professionals, both generally and specific to genetics.
- A4. EU-led campaign to promote general genetics knowledge and awareness of genetic cancer/disease predispositions in the population.
- A5. EU support (financial and/or regulatory) for generalized genetic counselling training and recognition pathways for existing health professionals (*e.g. nurses, non-geneticist physicians, molecular biologists/pathologists*).
- A6. EU support for the creation and hosting of digital tools capable of securely and efficiently collecting family history and other cancer risk data from patients.
- A7. EU regulation of direct-to-consumer genetic testing.
- A8. Dedicated EU funding to support new genetic counselling training programs in Member States (*e.g. continuing education for non-genetics health professionals; degree programs for genetic counsellors*).
- A9. EU-wide restriction of germline genetic testing to academic centers.
- A10. Establish a European genetic literacy institute to lead the development of European initiatives.

Importance and Urgency ratings for five of these aggregated solutions met consensus criteria (**Figure 3**); Importance but not Urgency ratings met consensus criteria for an additional two aggregated solutions. Cancer patient organization representatives were generally more positive regarding the Importance, Urgency, and Feasibility of Aggregated solutions – significant differences between professional groups noted in Figure 2 were mostly between positive ratings of cancer patient organization representatives and the more moderate ratings of one or more professional groups ($p < .05$). The exception to this is solution A8 related to EU funding for genetic counselling training, which genetic counsellors rated as being significantly more Urgent than clinical/medical geneticists ($p < .04$).

Priority rankings

Five solutions were ranked as Priority #1, #2, or #3 at least 15 times – P1, P2, P4, P7, P9. All other solutions received less than 9 total Priority rankings (**Figure 4**). Solutions P1 and P2 related to EU-wide recognition and education/accreditation of genetic counsellors were ranked significantly higher and more frequently by genetic counsellors compared to other professional groups ($p < .02$). Solution A1 related to the creation of online materials to support counselling was ranked significantly higher and more frequently by clinical/medical oncologists compared to other professional groups ($p < .03$).

Figure 2. Average Importance, Urgency and Feasibility ratings for solutions proposed in Phase 1. Consensus Importance and Urgency was defined a priori as an average rating >7. # - significant differences between professional groups, Importance rating ($p < .05$). * - significant differences between professional groups, Urgency rating ($p < .05$).

Figure 3. Average Importance, Urgency and Feasibility ratings for additional solutions aggregated from participant proposals in Phase 1; these aggregated solutions were rated by all participants in Phase 2. Consensus Importance and Urgency was defined a priori as an average rating >7. # - significant differences between professional groups, Importance rating ($p < .05$). * - significant differences between professional groups, Urgency rating ($p < .05$). ^ - significant differences between professional groups, Feasibility rating ($p < .05$).

Figure 4. Priority votes for researcher-proposed ('P' solutions; rated in Phase 1) and aggregated participant ('A' solutions; rated in Phase 2) solutions to common European barriers to genetic counselling. \$ - significant differences in prioritization between professional groups ($p < .05$).

Recommendations

Priority Recommendations

A clear top tier of priority European solutions for addressing common literacy, workforce and reimbursement barriers to genetic counselling in cancer was revealed through participant priority rankings (Figure 3). Five solutions received 15 or more total priority votes (combined Priority #1, #2, and #3), while no other solution received more than 9 votes. These five solutions all also exceeded consensus Importance and Urgency criteria, and are discussed below in descending order of the number of 'Priority #1' votes received:

EU-wide recognition of genetic counsellors as allied health professionals and appropriately qualified experts to deliver genetic counselling (P1).

Feasibility: Moderate (6.6/9); relatively lower Importance, Urgency, and/or Priority ratings from clinical/medical geneticists and clinical/medical oncologists compared to genetic counsellors presents an additional challenge to implementation.

Discussion: Legal recognition of genetic counsellors throughout EU Member States has been proposed previously,⁹ with work in this area currently underway within the European Board of Medical Genetics (EBMG), Genetic Nurse Genetic Counsellor Branch. Genetic counsellors, typically Master's degree qualified allied health professionals, have been demonstrated to deliver quality genetic counselling services across multiple clinical scenarios, and are recognized and well-integrated into health systems in e.g. Australia, the United Kingdom, and the United States.¹⁰ An estimated 570 trained genetic counsellors currently exist in Europe. However, their integration

into the delivery of genetic services in the EU is limited by a lack of professional recognition in all Member States except France. An estimated 340 of these genetic counsellors are present in 14 EU countries outside France, presenting a ready-made means of rapidly and broadly boosting genetic counselling workforce capacity.⁷

However, Delphi survey results indicate that additional dialogue with clinical/medical geneticists and oncologists is needed to ensure a broad mandate for concrete action towards EU-wide genetic counsellor recognition. Considering only the responses of clinical/medical geneticists and oncologists, Importance (7.2/9) but not Urgency (6.9/9) ratings would have met consensus criteria.

Immediate Action Steps: Host multi-stakeholder dialogues (clinical/medical geneticists and oncologists; genetic counsellors) to address concerns and pathways for genetic counsellor recognition, with a view to future concrete action.

Mandatory inclusion of genetics expertise in the creation and revision of national/EU clinical oncology guidelines (P9).

Feasibility: High (7.6/9)

Discussion: Genetics is increasingly integrated into oncology practice as part of the push towards precision/personalized medicine.¹¹ Accordingly, including a genetics expert into the process of creating and revising national and European oncology guidelines presents a common sense solution to ensuring optimal integration of genetics into oncology practice. Several Delphi survey participants noted that genetics expertise is already included in the creation and revision of national guidelines in their

Member States. An EU-wide mandate would facilitate equitable and expert integration of genetics into oncology practice across Member States.

Immediate Action Steps: Map the role of genetics expertise in the creation and revision of national clinical oncology guidelines in Member States to identify where updates to guideline creation/revision procedures are required. Engage in direct dialogue with the relevant national oncology societies to facilitate procedural updates.

P2 - Establish an EU system of registration, education and accreditation for genetic counsellors (allied health professional) with legal weight in Member States (P2).

Feasibility: Moderate (6.3/9); relatively lower Importance, Urgency, and/or Priority ratings from clinical/medical geneticists and clinical/medical oncologists compared to genetic counsellors presents an additional challenge to implementation.

Discussion: A concern noted in our preliminary work related to the recognition of genetic counsellors (Solution P1) was the high burden of establishing national registration/accreditation and education frameworks to serve a low number of health professionals.⁶ Accordingly, distributing this burden across Member States was envisioned as a means to support the legal recognition and better integration of genetic counsellors, particularly in the 26 Member States which do not presently recognize the genetic counselling profession (*exception: France*). Precedent for such a distributed and reciprocal education system already exists in some countries for other medical specialties – e.g. Luxembourg does not provide medical oncology

training, but recognizes medical oncology as a specialty and integrates medical oncologists trained abroad into their health system.¹²

Evidence of 63-100% 5-year growth in the genetic counselling profession in the US and Australia indicates that a European registration and education framework may only need to be an interim solution to support the growth of the genetic counselling profession in Europe.⁷ Once sufficient numbers of genetic counsellors exist in each Member State, registration and accreditation systems could be established at the national level, in line with other health professions.

A European system of registration for genetic counsellors and accreditation of genetic counselling education programs is already provided by the EBMG Genetic Nurse Genetic Counsellor Branch. However, this system does not presently carry any legal weight in Member States, limiting its ability to impact quality standards in genetic counselling practice and education – 140 genetic counsellors are currently registered with EBMG, of c. 570 genetic counsellors estimated to presently exist in EU Member States.⁷ Written comments in the Delphi survey indicated that some genetic counsellors regard EBMG registration as being overly burdensome, particularly given the unclear benefits to their ability to practice. Further, this system currently relies on voluntary contributions from members of the EBMG Genetic Nurse Genetic Counsellor Branch and has limited potential for sustainable expansion.

Similarly to Solution P1, the results of the Delphi survey indicate that additional dialogue with clinical/medical geneticists and oncologists is needed to build a clearer mandate for concrete action. Considering only the responses of clinical/medical geneticists and oncologists, Importance (7.2/9) but not Urgency (6.6/9) ratings would have met consensus criteria.

Immediate Action Steps: Include issues related to proposed European genetic counsellor registration and education frameworks within multi-stakeholder dialogues for genetic counsellor recognition proposed in relation to Solution P1.

Mandatory education for clinical oncologists – continuing and as a part of fellowship training – regarding screening for cancer predisposition syndromes (e.g. when to refer, how to screen) (P7).

Feasibility: High (7.1/9)

Discussion: As noted above and in the latest (2016) global recommendations for oncology fellowship curricula from the European Society for Medical Oncology (ESMO) and American Society for Clinical Oncology (ASCO), genetics competencies are now required to deliver best-practice medical oncology.¹³ However, both our prior work and the results of this Delphi survey indicate that present fellowship and continuing education programs for medical oncologists do not sufficiently support the acquisition of these competencies.⁶

Recent research notes that tailored education specific to the needs of oncologists – i.e. as compared to generalized training in cancer predisposition syndromes – best supports genetics competency acquisition and integration.¹⁴ The availability of such tailored education is presently sparse: no ongoing continuing education programs in cancer genetics were found in any European Union Member State for any health professionals, not just medical oncologists, in a 2022 review.¹⁵ A bi-annual 2-day cancer predisposition preceptorship course has been delivered for medical oncologists by ESMO in conjunction with the European Reference Network on Genetic

Tumor Risk Syndromes (ERN GENTURIS) since 2019, but requires in-person attendance for most attendees.

The integration of genetics training into medical oncology fellowships across the EU is also unclear. The ESMO/ASCO curricular recommendations are presently only fully implemented in four Member States, with these recommendations noted as being ‘adapted’ or ‘partially integrated’ into fellowship training in a further 11 Member States.¹² Whether and how genetics information is included in fellowship training in circumstances where ESMO/ASCO recommendations are adapted or partially integration has not been chronicled.

Accordingly, the importance of genetics education for medical oncologists is broadly acknowledged but not presently reflected in current educational offerings across the EU. A European mandate for the inclusion of genetics in oncology fellowships and compulsory continuing education promises to provide a necessary impetus to close this gap.

Immediate Action Steps: Map the inclusion of genetics information in oncology fellowship curricula in EU Member States. Consult with European (e.g. ESMO, ERN GENTURIS) and national (e.g. national medical oncology societies) stakeholders to appraise what would be required to support the provision of genetics information to all oncologists through fellowships and/or continuing education initiatives.

Mandate full reimbursement of genetic counselling when conducted according to national or European guidelines (P4).

Feasibility: Moderate (6.2/9)

Discussion: Our preliminary work noted that reimbursement of/payment for genetic counselling services was at least partly limited for health practitioners and/or patients in 13 of 27 Member States.⁶ This is despite the broad inclusion of genetic counselling in clinical practice guidelines and, indeed, national legislation – in several Member States, incomplete reimbursement for counselling persists despite the existence of legal mandates for pre- and/or post-test genetic counselling.⁶ The unclear economic utility of genetic counselling is likely at least partly responsible,¹⁶ with further work needed to ensure the universal inclusion of genetic counselling within emerging personalized medicine reimbursement models.¹⁷ Similarly to our notes related to Solution P7 above, a European reimbursement mandate promises to close remaining gaps related to genetic counselling; this mandate would be aided by clear demonstrations of long-term economic utility and sustainability.

Immediate Action Steps: Needs assessment/consultation with national health insurance schemes in the 13 Member States with persisting genetic counselling reimbursement limitations to determine pathways to full reimbursement. As appropriate, further economic analyses to support health insurances in providing full reimbursement.

Summary and Conclusions

Common European barriers to genetic counselling quality and access in cancer were identified in preliminary work (Deliverable 5.3 + survey of cancer patient organizations): genetic literacy (*of patients and non-genetics health professionals*); workforce capacity; and insurance reimbursement. Through a Delphi survey of genetics, oncology, and patient stakeholders from across the EU, five priority European solutions were identified to address these common barriers:

- 1) EU-wide recognition of genetic counsellors
- 2) inclusion of genetics expertise in the creation and updating of oncology guidelines
- 3) EU system of registration, accreditation, and education for genetic counsellors
- 4) Mandatory fellowship and continuing education in genetics for oncologists
- 5) Mandatory full reimbursement of genetic counselling when clinical guidelines are met

Feasibility ratings of these priority solutions indicate that solutions related to oncology guidelines and fellowship/continuing education will likely be the most straightforward and quickest to implement. Solutions related to reimbursement and genetic counsellor recognition/registration/accreditation/education are still high priority but will likely require extended timeframes and additional effort towards implementation. Immediate next steps proposed for each solution include mapping, multi-stakeholder discussion, and economic analysis activities. Inclusion of work related to these immediate next steps in the upcoming Joint Action on Personalized Cancer Medicine is currently under discussion.

Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our gratitude to the 35 participants of our interview survey of health professionals, 20 participants of our survey of cancer patient organizations, and 77 participants of the Delphi survey for their contributions to the development of these recommendations.

References

1. Resta R, Biesecker BB, Bennett RL, et al. A new definition of genetic counseling: National Society of Genetic Counselors' task force report. *Journal of Genetic Counseling* 2006;15:77-83.
2. Bensend TA, Veach PM, Niendorf KB. What's the harm? Genetic counselor perceptions of adverse effects of genetics service provision by non-genetics professionals. *Journal of Genetic Counseling* 2014;23:48-63.
3. Dragojlovic N, Kopac N, Borle K, et al. Utilization and uptake of clinical genetics services in high-income countries: a scoping review. *Health Policy* 2021;125(7):877-887.
4. Abacan M, Alsubaie L, Barlow-Stewart K, et al. The global state of the genetic counseling profession. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 2019;27(2):183-197.
5. Dragojlovic N, Borle K, Kopac N, et al. The composition and capacity of the clinical genetics workforce in high-income countries: a scoping review. *Genetics in Medicine* 2020;22(9):1437-1449.
6. McCrary JM, Van Valckenborgh E, Poirel HA, et al. Genetic counselling legislation and practice in cancer in EU Member States. *European Journal of Public Health* 2024:ckae093.
7. Ormond KE, Abad PJ, MacLeod R, Nishigaki M, Wessels T-M. The global status of genetic counselors in 2023: What has changed in the past 5 years? *Genetics in Medicine Open* 2024:101887.
8. Khodyakov D, Grant S, Kroger J, Bauman M. RAND methodological guidance for conducting and critically appraising Delphi panels: RAND, 2023.
9. Paneque M, Liehr T, Serra Juhé C, Moog U, Melegh B, Carreira I. The need for recognition of core professional groups in genetics healthcare services in Europe. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 2022;30(6):639-640.
10. Skirton H, Cordier C, Ingvoldstad C, Taris N, Benjamin C. The role of the genetic counsellor: a systematic review of research evidence. *European Journal of Human Genetics* 2015;23(4):452-458.
11. Yates L, Seoane J, Le Tourneau C, et al. The European society for medical oncology (ESMO) precision medicine glossary. *Annals of Oncology* 2018;29(1):30-35.
12. Cufer T, Kosty M, Osterlund P, et al. Current landscape of ESMO/ASCO Global Curriculum adoption and medical oncology recognition: a global survey. *ESMO Open* 2021;6(6):100219.

13. Dittrich C, Kosty M, Jezdic S, et al. ESMO/ASCO recommendations for a global curriculum in medical oncology edition 2016. *ESMO Open* 2016;1(5):e000097
14. Rahman B, McEwen A, Phillips JL, Tucker K, Goldstein D, Jacobs C. Genetic and genomic learning needs of oncologists and oncology nurses in the era of precision medicine: A scoping review. *Personalized Medicine* 2022;19(2):139-153.
15. Hoxhaj I, Beccia F, Calabrò GE, Boccia S. A web screening on training initiatives in cancer genomics for healthcare professionals. *Genes* 2022;13(3):430.
16. Payne K, Eden M. Measuring the economic value of genetic counselling. *European journal of medical genetics* 2019;62(5):385-389.
17. Koleva-Kolarova R, Buchanan J, Vellekoop H, et al. Financing and reimbursement models for personalised medicine: a systematic review to identify current models and future options. *Applied Health Economics and Health Policy* 2022;20(4):501-524.

Appendix A – Survey of cancer patient organizations regarding genetic counselling in cancer

Survey Background

You have been invited to complete this survey because you are a cancer patient organization in an EU Member State with coverage of cancer types likely to have included some patient interaction with genetics (e.g. breast, lung, colorectal, rare cancers). Thank you in advance for your contributions!

This survey is being conducted as part of the European Commission-funded CAN.HEAL Consortium (<https://canheal.eu>) – one of the aims of this Consortium is to develop recommendations regarding strategies to improve genetic counselling quality and access across EU Member States. Results of this survey will be combined with results of an interview survey of health professionals from each EU Member State to form a basis for recommendations.

Please answer all questions according to the best of your knowledge - we are most interested in your perceptions and perspective. All responses will be stored on secure servers according to GDPR regulations. Neither your name nor the name of your cancer patient organization will be included in any public materials (e.g. *publications, presentations*) related to this survey without explicit consent. Please direct questions, comments, and concerns to the coordinator of this survey, Dr. J. Matt McCrary from Hannover Medical School (mccrary.james@mh-hannover.de).

Background Information on Genetic Counselling in Cancer

Genetic counselling – defined broadly as ‘the process of helping people understand and adapt to the medical, psychological and familial implications of genetic contributions to disease’ – is critical to the effective integration of genetics into cancer care. It provides a key human interface point between patients and physicians/allied healthcare professionals with regard to genetics in cancer care. The specific individuals delivering genetic counselling vary from country to country, and include physicians (specialized in genetics, from non-genetics specialties, general practitioners), nurses (with and without additional genetics training), and genetic counsellors (Master’s degree qualified allied health specialists).

Genetic counselling can be delivered at two key timepoints: before and after a genetic test. Genetic counseling before a genetic test (i.e. **pre-test counselling**) aims to enable patients and their families to make informed decisions about how and when to include genetic testing in their cancer care journeys. Genetic counselling after a genetic test (i.e. **post-test counselling**) assists patients and their families in interpreting and responding to the results of a genetic test. This applies in both predictive and clinical scenarios (defined for reference below).

Predictive genetic testing - genetic testing performed in healthy individuals to provide insights into future cancer risks and inform potential risk management strategies for these individuals and/or their families.

Clinical genetic testing - genetic testing performed in patients with active cancer disease to provide insights into potential hereditary/genetic contributions to their disease and inform treatment strategies. Clinical genetic tests can also have implications for cancer risk in family members of patients.

The importance of genetic counselling in cancer care is widely acknowledged. However, organizing the timely, accessible and high-quality delivery of genetic counselling is a complex endeavor, particularly given exponential increases in genetic testing occurring alongside increasing shortages of health professionals with genetics expertise.

Survey

1. How often is genetic counselling provided before a genetic test in your country?
 - a. Always
 - b. Often
 - c. Sometimes
 - d. Rarely
 - e. Never

2. How often is genetic counselling provided after a genetic test (i.e. to discuss results) in your country?
 - a. Always
 - b. Often
 - c. Sometimes
 - d. Rarely
 - e. Never

3. Please indicate how often cost and/or insurance coverage is a barrier to patients receiving genetic counselling **in a treatment scenario** in your country:
 - a. Always
 - b. Frequently
 - c. Sometimes
 - d. Rarely
 - e. Never

4. Please indicate how often cost and/or insurance coverage is a barrier to patients receiving genetic counselling **in a predictive scenario** in your country:
 - a. Always
 - b. Frequently
 - c. Sometimes
 - d. Rarely
 - e. Never

5. Who provides genetic counselling **before** a genetic test in your country? (*check all that apply*)
 - a. The medical doctor (genetics specialty) who prescribed the test
 - b. The medical doctor (non-genetics specialty, including general practitioners) who prescribed the test
 - c. The nurse who prescribed the test
 - d. The genetic counsellor (Master's degree qualified specialist allied health professional) who prescribed the test
 - e. A medical doctor (genetics specialty) who didn't prescribe the test
 - f. A medical doctor (non-genetics specialty, including general practitioners) who didn't prescribe the test
 - g. A nurse who didn't prescribe the test
 - h. A genetic counsellor (Master's degree qualified specialist allied health professional) who didn't prescribe the test

6. Who provides genetic counselling **after** a genetic test in your country? (*check all that apply*)
 - a. The medical doctor (genetics specialty) who prescribed the test
 - b. The medical doctor (non-genetics specialty, including general practitioners) who prescribed the test
 - c. The nurse who prescribed the test
 - d. The genetic counsellor (Master's degree qualified specialist allied health professional) who prescribed the test
 - e. A medical doctor (genetics specialty) who didn't prescribe the test
 - f. A medical doctor (non-genetics specialty, including general practitioners) who didn't prescribe the test
 - g. A nurse who didn't prescribe the test
 - h. A genetic counsellor (Master's degree qualified specialist allied health professional) who didn't prescribe the test

7. Please indicate the preferred mode of delivery of pre-test genetic counselling:
 - a. Phone/video for most patients
 - b. Face-to-face for most patients
 - c. Phone/video for most patients living in rural areas, face-to-face for most patients living in cities
 - d. No clear preference

8. Please indicate the preferred mode of delivery of post-test genetic counselling when no significant results were found:
 - a. Phone/video for most patients
 - b. Face-to-face for most patients
 - c. Phone/video for most patients living in rural areas, face-to-face for most patients living in cities
 - d. No clear preference

9. Please indicate the preferred mode of delivery of post-test genetic counselling when significant genetic alterations were found:
 - a. Phone/video for most patients
 - b. Face-to-face for most patients
 - c. Phone/video for most patients living in rural areas, face-to-face for most patients living in cities
 - d. No clear preference

10. Please rate general patient perceptions regarding the waiting time for receiving genetic counselling **before** a genetic test **in a clinical scenario** in your country:
 - a. Waiting times are far too long
 - b. Waiting times are too long
 - c. Waiting times are long but manageable
 - d. Waiting times are OK
 - e. Waiting times are excellent

11. Please rate general patient perceptions regarding the waiting time for receiving genetic counselling **after** a genetic test **in a clinical scenario** in your country:
 - a. Waiting times are far too long
 - b. Waiting times are too long
 - c. Waiting times are long but manageable
 - d. Waiting times are OK
 - e. Waiting times are excellent

12. Please rate general patient perceptions regarding the waiting time for receiving genetic counselling **before** a genetic test **in a predictive scenario** in your country:
 - a. Waiting times are far too long
 - b. Waiting times are too long
 - c. Waiting times are long but manageable
 - d. Waiting times are OK
 - e. Waiting times are excellent

13. Please rate general patient perceptions regarding the waiting time for receiving genetic counselling **after** a genetic test (**in a predictive scenario** in your country):
 - a. Waiting times are far too long
 - b. Waiting times are too long
 - c. Waiting times are long but manageable
 - d. Waiting times are OK
 - e. Waiting times are excellent
14. Please rate the **availability of** additional psychosocial support to help patients/families deal with the consequences of their diagnosis:
 - a. 0 – 10 Likert rating
15. Please rate the **need for** additional psychosocial support to help patients/families deal with the consequences of their diagnosis:
 - a. 0 – 10 Likert rating
16. Please rate the **availability of** additional resources designed to help patients understand genetic information presented during genetic counselling
 - a. 0 – 10 Likert rating
17. Please rate **the need for** additional resources designed to help patients understand genetic information presented during genetic counselling
 - a. 0 – 10 Likert rating
18. Please rate the **availability of** resources designed to help patients understand the potential importance of genetics in preventing and treating cancer
 - a. 0 – 10 Likert rating
19. Please rate the **need for** additional resources designed to help patients understand the potential importance of genetics in preventing and treating cancer
 - a. 0 – 10 Likert rating
20. Please detail any other barriers to patient access to genetic counselling in your country that have not been addressed by the questions above (*if all have been addressed, please write 'all addressed'*)
 - a. Free text entry
21. Please describe the most important change that could be made to improve patient access to and/or experiences with genetics in cancer prevention and care
 - a. Free text entry

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